

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

KNOWLEDGE, PRACTICE AND BARRIERS TO FOLLOW RECOMMENDED GUIDELINES FOR MEASURING BLOOD PRESSURE AMONG PRIMARY HEALTH CARE NURSES IN JEDDAH 2018/2019.

Dr. Amna Osama Jamjoom, MBBS, Dr. Khadija Hassan Eid, MBBS,
Dr Abdulhameed M. Hassan, MBBS.
Consultant Family Medicine.

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Background: Hypertension is among the most common conditions examined in PHC. Moreover, hypertension leads to many comorbidities such as renal failure, myocardial infarction, strokes, and if not appropriately treated leads to early death. Approximately 20% of world's population is hypertensive it is also called "silent killer" because it often has no symptoms, that's precisely why it is essential for people to check their blood pressure regularly. Accurately measuring blood pressure, is a critical skill that must be performed with practice and proper training by the person obtaining the reading because many factors will affect the accuracy of the reading. Patients' Blood pressure is usually obtained by nurses; it is clinically important for the blood pressure reading to be accurate for the physician to manage the patient correctly and avoid over diagnosing or over the treatment of hypertension. This issue is of high importance to the individuals and community since it's one of the top common diseases. Hypertension is a preventable disease if managed well. There are no studies carried out locally, and only a few similar studies performed internationally; being said, this makes this topic of high importance.

Subject and Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in 25 primary health care centers in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, which were selected using a multi-stage stratified sampling technique.

Main Results: Reliability analysis showed good internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha for full observer-assessed questionnaire (0.915), Patient-Related Standards (0.881), Equipment-Related Standards (0.741), and Examiner-Related Standards (0.804) subscales. Regarding Patient-Related Standards, compliance rates varied depending on the standard and ranged from 9.0% for measuring blood pressure in standing position if postural hypotension is suspected to 98.1% for measuring blood pressure in sitting position with back supported, where applicable. Regarding Equipment-Related Standards, compliance rates ranged between 50.0% for correct stethoscope position maintained to 98.8% for adequate cuff wrapping around the upper arm. Regarding Examiner-Related Standards, given the use of automated instruments, 6 out of the 10 standards were not applicable for majority of the participants; however, compliance rate was relatively high. No statistically significant association of practice was found with nurse's gender, nationality, years of experience and degree. Among the investigated barriers, only lack of proper training was associated with low practice levels in Patient-Related Standards (mean [SD] PRSS=0.49 [0.10] versus 0.59 [0.17], $p=0.029$) and ERS (mean [SD] ERSS=0.65 [0.13] versus 0.75 [0.16], $p=0.031$) compared to absence of this barrier, respectively. As to self-assessed practice, analysis showed relatively high compliance rates with majority of the standards.

Conclusion and recommendation: Our study showed high knowledge and practice levels for BP measurement among a sample of nurses regarding providing a pre-measurement rest to the patient, back and elbow support, cuff position, and rounding the values to 2 mmHg as well as moderate practice levels about measuring BP in both arms, undressing patients' arms and following the specific guidelines. Nonetheless, the participants exhibited inadequate practice levels regarding several parameters, including the assurance of bladder distension, measuring BP twice at each visit, and measuring BP in a standing position if postural hypotension is suspected.

Findings from this study corroborate the importance of addressing blood pressure measurement errors by raising awareness about the implied guidelines and providing regular and frequent training to nurses, including students and more experienced ones.

Key Words: Knowledge, Practice, Barriers, Blood Pressure, Primary Health Care, Nurses.

Corresponding authors:**Dr Amna Jamjoom***Resident Family Medicine, Joint Program, Jeddah, KSA,**Alshatae dist, Jeddah KSA**0966506662259, Amnaoj91@gmail.com***Dr Khadija Eid,***Resident Family Medicine, Joint Program, Jeddah, KSA,**Alshatae dist, Jeddah KSA, 00966503707232, Eid.khadijah@gmail.com*

Please cite this article in press Amna Jamjoom / Khadija Eid et al., *Knowledge, Practice And Barriers To Follow Recommended Guidelines For Measuring Blood Pressure Among Primary Health Care Nurses In Jeddah 2018/2019., Indo Am. J. P. Sci., 2019; 06[06].*

INTRODUCTION:

Blood pressure (BP) measurement is the most commonly performed clinical maneuver in medical settings. It was as early as 1855 when the first sphygmograph has been invented for indirect BP measurement⁽¹⁾, while the first portable non-invasive means of measuring the ambulatory BP was described in 1962⁽²⁾. Since then, a number of devices have been developed, with the brachial artery being the standard location of taking their readings. These methods provide simple, non-invasive and painless methods of measurement.

Traditionally, mercury sphygmomanometers were used as the gold standard methods for office measurements. However, with the ban implied on these devices due to potential mercury toxicity and the associated problems with its disposal, aneroid devices have emerged^(3, 4). Such devices showed marked variations in their error rates, ranging between 1% and 44%⁽⁵⁻⁷⁾ although validation studies revealed insignificant differences in BP measurements between mercury and aneroid devices^(8, 9). Even when compared to the recently-introduced digital (automated or oscillometric) sphygmomanometers, the aneroid devices had superior sensitivity and specificity rates for measuring both systolic and diastolic BPs⁽¹⁰⁾.

However, BP readings using these devices are often inconsistent or inappropriate, leading to under- or over-estimation and subsequently could be associated with improper treatment⁽¹¹⁾. An erroneous diagnosis may also be accompanied by unfavorable social and economic costs. Furthermore, evidence has shown that small variations in BP readings may have a significant effect on cardiovascular and cerebrovascular risk⁽¹²⁾. As such, BP measurements should be accurate and reliable with minimal errors.

Several causes of errors in BP readings have been reported and they frequently involve the patient or the physician/healthcare provider. Pre-measurement exercise and smoking as well as talking during measurement are the most reportedly patient-related factors. One of the major contributing factors is the temporary increase of blood pressure occurring at the time of a clinic visit, namely the white coat effect⁽¹³⁾, due to the conditional or hyperactive alerting responses to viewing the physician. Importantly, the sex and race of the observer, as well as the rate of cuff deflation, have been established as observer-related factors.

Therefore, several strategies have been proposed to reduce pitfalls in measurement, including forgoing a cup of coffee or a cigarette, taking at least two readings, adopting a relatively quick deflation (at 3 mmHg per second), proper cuff bladder size, and correct patient positioning (in a sitting position with the arm supported at the heart level)⁽¹¹⁾. In this context, BP measurement should be performed by a trained healthcare provider.

More specifically, nurses are the most concerned staff as they are frequently involved in BP measurement. Studies revealed that healthcare providers, including nurses, often show a lack of adherence to measurement guidelines⁽¹⁴⁾, representing a significant threat to diagnostic and management approaches. This is of particular importance in Saudi Arabia since the prevalence of prehypertension and hypertension could reach up to 54.9% and 4.9%, respectively⁽¹⁵⁾. On the other hand, when nurses comply with the guidelines, their readings are closely correlated with the real BP values than those usually obtained at the clinic⁽¹⁶⁾. The role of nurses can extend to alleviate erroneous results by reducing the white coat effect⁽¹⁷⁾.

In Saudi Arabia, little is known about the current patterns of knowledge and practice as well as the

adherence to BP measurement guidelines at the primary healthcare centers (PHC), where large numbers of patients are checked daily. The current study aimed to assess the level of practice in BP measurement among PHC nurses in reference to guidelines and good practice checklists. Their levels of self-reported knowledge and practice were also assessed as well as the barriers to executing proper measurement techniques. Finally, we investigated the professional factors that could be associated with BP measurement accuracy.

SUBJECT AND METHOD:

Study Design: A multi-center cross-sectional study was conducted in primary health care centers (PHCC) in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia, 2018-2019.

Study Population and Sample Technique: This study included Nurses in primary care centers in Jeddah, A multistage stratified sampling technique was used to include 25 PHCCs out of the 47 existing in the locality. In stage one, PHCCs were divided into 5 strata in agreement with their 5 referral hospitals including King Abdullah Medical complex, King Abdul-Aziz Hospital, East Jeddah General Hospital, King Fahad General Hospital and Al-Thaghr Hospital. In stage 2, 5 PHCCS were randomly selected out of each sector (stratum). In stage 3, a convenience sampling technique was used to include equivalent number of participants from each sector.

Research Instrument And Data Collection: This study used a semi-structured questionnaire, which contains two main parts corresponding to two phases of the study: 1. *Observer-assessed practice (OAP):* This first phase consisted of an audit, in which the investigator blindly observed nurses' practice in BP measurement and assessed their compliance with a pre-designed standards' checklist. The checklist contains three subscales including Patient-Related Standards (PRS) (13 items), Equipment-Related Standards (EQRS) (8 items) and Examiner-Related Standards (ERS) (10 items). For each standard, the nurse was rated as compliant or non-compliant; and in case if the standard was not applicable, the corresponding item was removed from the scale. Each nurse was observed during one BP measurement session. A practice score was then calculated as described further. 2. *Self-assessed practice;* This phase used a self-administered questionnaire investigating the practice in BP measurement (13

items) and barriers to applying proper technique (4 items). The two questionnaires were designed by the researcher and underwent face and content validity by a consultants' committee. Further, the questionnaire was translated to Arabic for Arabic-speaking participants; the translated version was back-translated to English and showed >80% similarity with the original English version.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Statistical analysis was performed with the Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 21.0 for Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Descriptive statistics were used to present participants' characteristics and the patterns of answers to the self-assessed and observer-assessed practice. Categorical variables are presented as frequency and percentage, while discrete variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Reliability of the observer-assessed practice scale (31 items) and subscales (PRS [13 items], EQRS [8 items], and ERS [10 items]) was analyzed by calculation of Cronbach's alpha. Factors of practice in BP measurement were analyzed by analyzing the variance of the 3 subscales scores (PRSS, EQRSS, and ERSS) across the factors categories; analysis used independent *t*-test and Oneway Analysis of Variance (Oneway Anova) test as appropriate. A *p* value of <0.05 was considered to reject the null hypothesis.

Ethical considerations: Written approval from the local research committee of the Joint Program of Family Medicine-Jeddah was obtained before conducting the study.

Written permission and ethical approval from Medical Research and Studies Department at Directorate of health affairs – Jeddah.

Permission from all managers of participated PHCC was obtained.

Verbal consent from each nurse to participate in the study was a prerequisite for data collection.

RESULT:

Participants' characteristics: Two hundred and sixteen nurses were evaluated for BP measurement practice, 79.2% females, 95.4% national Saudis. Majority had diploma degree (80.1%) and 4-5 years of experience (56.9%) (Table 1).

Table 1: Participants' characteristics (N=216)

§: A respondent may use more than one instrument; PRS: patient-related standards score; EQRS: equipment-related

Parameter	Frequency	Percentage
Measuring BP for each patient as part of vital signs	208	96.3
Instrument used §		
Aneroid	14	6.5
Automated	206	95.4
Mercury	33	15.3
Hybrid	1	0.5
Following any guideline	89	41.2
Allow patient to rest physically for 3-5 minutes before measuring BP	194	89.8
Let patient relax in a quiet environment before measurement	179	82.9
BP measured while patient in sitting position	208	96.3
BP measured while patient's back supported	213	98.6
BP measured while patient has crossing of legs	182	84.3
BP measured while patient is not talking	189	87.5
In initial visit, do you measure BP in both arms	92	42.6
Measure BP with elbow supported	201	93.1
BP measured with upper arm cuffed at heart level	204	94.4
BP measured with patient's arm undressed by clothes	80	37.0
Asking patient about consuming caffeine or cigarette one hour before measurement	137	63.4
Asking patient if he is having a full urinary bladder before measurement	66	30.6
Examiner-assessed practice		
PRS (mean, SD)	0.58	0.17
EQRSS (mean, SD)	0.85	0.25
ERSS (mean, SD)	0.74	0.16

standards score; ERS: examiner-related standards score.

Self-assessed practice: The most frequent instrument used is automated (95.4%), followed by mercury (15.3%) and Aneroid (6.5%). Self-assessed practice showed relatively high compliance rates with majority of the standards, such as measuring BP for each patient (96.3%), allow patient to rest physically for 3-5 minutes before measurement (89.8%), BP measured in sitting position (96.3%), with patient's back supported (98.6%) and elbow supported (93.1%). However, self-assessed practice was relatively low in measuring BP in both arms at initial visit (42.6%), undressing patient's arms (37.0%) and asking the patient whether he/she has a full urinary bladder before assessment (30.6%). Further, only 41.2% declared following any guideline in BP measurement (Table 2).

Table 2: Self-assessed practice in BP measurement

Parameter	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	171	79,2
	Male	37	17,1
	N.S	8	3,7
Nationality	Saudi	206	95,4
	Non-Saudi	7	3,2
	N.S	3	1,4
Years of experience	<1	12	5,6
	1-<3	19	8,8
	3-<5	44	20,4
	≥5	123	56,9
	N.S	18	8,3
Degree	Bachelor's of Nursing	38	17,6
	Diploma of Nursing	173	80,1
	N.S	5	2,3

N.S: not specified;

Observer-assessed practice: Regarding PRS, compliance rates varied depending on the standard and ranged from 9.0% for measuring BP in standing position if postural hypotension is suspected to 98.1% for measuring BP in sitting position with back supported, where applicable. Regarding EQRS, compliance rates ranged between 50.0% for correct stethoscope position maintained (where applicable) to 98.8% for adequate cuff wrapping around the upper arm. Regarding ERS, given the use of automated instruments, 6 out of the 10 standards were not applicable for majority of the participants; however, compliance rate was high (86.1% to 99.2%) for the remaining standards, except for measuring BP twice at each visit and documenting the mean value, which was very low (16.9%) (Table 4, Figures 1, 2, and 3).

Table 3: Reliability of the examiner-assessed questionnaire subscales

Scale / subscale	No. items	Cronbach's alpha
Full questionnaire	31	0.915
Patient-related standards (PRS)	13	0.881
Equipment-related standards (EQRS)	8	0.741
Examiner-related standards (ERS)	10	0.804

Table 4: Examiner-assessed practice

Subscale / step	Yes	No	N/A	C.R
Patient-Related Standards				
1. Patient should have 3–5 minutes of physical rest before measuring BP.	148	60	7	71.2
2. Patient should relax in a quiet environment before measurement.	155	52	7	74.9
3. BP should be measured in sitting position.	202	4	7	98.1
4. Back of the patient should be supported while sitting for measurement.	196	11	7	94.7
5. Patient's legs should not be crossed while measuring.	184	23	7	88.9
6. Patient should not be talking while measuring.	138	69	7	66.7
7. BP measurement should be taken in both arms at initial visit.	32	154	25	17.2
8. The arm with the higher BP values should be noted in the chart and follow up should be performed on this arm.	64	124	22	34.0
9. Upper arm should not be covered by clothing.	71	136	8	34.3
10. Elbow should be supported and upper arm cuffed at heart level.	169	34	7	83.3
11. BP should be measured in standing position, if postural hypotension is suspected (e.g., diabetics and elderly patients >65 year).	13	131	71	9.0
12. Patient should avoid nicotine and caffeine one hour before BP measurement.	83	106	26	43.9
13. Patients should avoid measurement while the urinary bladder is distended.	38	153	24	19.9
Equipment-Related Standards				
1. Appropriate cuff size; cuff bladder should encircle 80% of the arm, and the cuff width should be 40% of the arm circumference.	173	32	8	84.4
2. Correct cuff position:				
a- A distance of 2.5 cm (2 fingers) should be maintained between the lower end of the cuff and the antecubital fossa.	179	26	7	87.3
b- Cuff bladder should be centered over the brachial artery.	187	17	7	91.7
c- Cuff should be wrapped around the upper arm, but not too tight and not too loose.	170	2	33	98.8
3. Correct stethoscope position:				
a- Correct stethoscope position; the bell orifice of the stethoscope should be placed just above and medial to the antecubital fossa but below the edge of the cuff.	3	3	202	50.0
b- The stethoscope bell orifice should not touch the cuff bladder or tubing.	3	2	202	60.0
4. Correct manometer position; The position of the mercury manometer should be upright at examiner's eye level, and at zero level.	11	1	196	91.7
5. The Equipment calibrated periodically.	108	20	79	84.4
Examiner-Related Standards				
1. Inflate the cuff bladder rapidly to 30 mm Hg above the level at which the radial pulse is extinguished.	6	2	195	75.0

Subscale / step	Yes	No	N/A	C.R
2. Apply mild pressure on the stethoscope bell (steadily and gently, without excessive pressure).	5	0	198	100.0
3. Deflate the cuff bladder pressure at the rate of 2 mm Hg/sec	6	2	195	75.0
4. Deflate the cuff bladder rapidly and completely at DBP to avoid venous congestion.	5	2	195	71.4
5. The SBP is defined as the cuff pressure at which the Korotkoff sound can be heard with the stethoscope (Phase I), and the DBP as the cuff pressure at which the Korotkoff sound disappears over the brachial artery (Phase V).	3	4	196	42.9
6. Avoid reinflation and correction of stethoscope position during the measurement.	3	2	197	60.0
7. BP should be measured at least twice at each visit and the mean value documented.	21	103	78	16.9
8. Record SBP and DBP immediately, rounded off to 2 mm Hg.	105	17	80	86.1
9. Repeat BP measurement if necessary after a break of 1 min.	120	1	81	99.2
10. BP measurements should always be associated with measurement of heart rate	120	1	81	99.2

C.R: Compliance rate, calculated as the percentage of nurses who complied with the given item among all participants, by exclusion of those where the item was not applicable

Figure 1: Assessment of patient-related standards. Bars represent the percentage of nurses who complied with the given standard among all participants, by exclusion of not-applicable cases.

Figure 2: Assessment of equipment-related standards. Bars represent the percentage of nurses who complied with the given standard among all participants, by exclusion of not-applicable cases.

Figure 3: Assessment of examiner-related standards. Bars represent the percentage of nurses who complied with the given standard among all participants, by exclusion of not-applicable cases.

Factors of Practice in Bp Measurement: No statistically significant association of PRSS, EQRSS or ERSS was found with nurse's gender, nationality, years of experience and degree ($p>0.050$). Among barriers to applying proper BP measurement technique, only lack of proper training was associated with low practice levels in PRS (mean [SD] PRSS=0.49 [0.10] versus 0.59 [0.17], $p=0.029$) and ERS (mean [SD] ERSS=0.65 [0.13] versus 0.75 [0.16], $p=0.031$) compared to absence of this barrier, respectively. Paradoxically, increased workload entailed higher EQRSS (mean [SD]=0.91 [0.21]) compared to absence of increased workload (0.82 [0.26]), and the difference was statistically significant ($p=0.009$) (Table 5).

Table 5: Factors associated with practice in BP measurement

Parameter	Category	PRSS		EQRSS		ERSS	
		Mean (SD)	p-value	Mean (SD)	p-value	Mean (SD)	p-value
Gender	Female	0.60 (0.17)		0.85 (0.24)		0.74 (0.16)	
	Male	0.54 (0.17)	.050	0.87 (0.25)	.703	0.75 (0.13)	.772
Nationality	Saudi	0.59 (0.17)		0.86 (0.24)		0.74 (0.16)	
	Non-Saudi	0.49 (0.21)	.136	0.70 (0.34)	.101	0.75 (0.00)	.915
Years of experience	<1	0.55 (0.19)		0.79 (0.22)		0.75 (0.14)	
	1-<2	0.53 (0.12)		0.86 (0.27)		0.74 (0.13)	
	2-<4	0.55 (0.14)		0.87 (0.24)		0.68 (0.11)	
	4-<5	0.59 (0.17)	.400	0.85 (0.26)	.816	0.75 (0.17)	.292
Degree	38	0.60 (0.15)		0.92 (0.13)		0.72 (0.11)	
	173	0.58 (0.18)	.667	0.84 (0.27)	.052	0.75 (0.17)	.318
Time limitation	No	0.58 (0.18)		0.83 (0.25)		0.73 (0.13)	
	Yes	0.60 (0.16)	.434	0.88 (0.24)	.178	0.75 (0.18)	.448
Workload	No	0.58 (0.16)		0.82 (0.26)		0.72 (0.14)	
	Yes	0.60 (0.18)	.555	0.91 (0.21)	.009*	0.76 (0.17)	.124
Lack of privacy in facility	No	0.59 (0.18)		0.84 (0.26)		0.74 (0.17)	
	Yes	0.55 (0.14)	.192	0.91 (0.17)	.148	0.75 (0.08)	.786
Lack of proper training	No	0.59 (0.17)		0.85 (0.25)		0.75 (0.16)	
	Yes	0.49 (0.10)	.029*	0.92 (0.17)	.294	0.65 (0.13)	.031*

DISCUSSION:

Implementing standardized and rigorous methods for BP measurement is imperative to ensure that the obtained readings are accurate and comparable for patients whom BP could differ due to diurnal variation, measurement error, and short- and long-term variability⁽²⁵⁾. Multiple methodological issues lead to substantial changes in BP when the assessment is not in compliance with the established standards. Not surprisingly, the role of nurses in BP measurement should be the main focus of research regarding the accuracy of BP measurement. In the current study, we showed that nurses had moderate compliance with measurement guidelines as revealed by self-reported parameters, while moderate to weak practice levels were reported by the examiners. Importantly, less than half of the participants declared compliance to any guidelines.

Our rate of nursing knowledge and practice was in agreement with that reported previously. González-López et al.⁽²⁶⁾ showed that approximately half of the participating nursing students were aware about several domains, such as those related to BP reading to the nearest 2 mmHg, cuff deflation rate and crossing legs during measurement. Nolan and Nolan⁽²⁷⁾ showed that only 40% of nurses had measured BP to the nearest 2 mmHg, 52% perceived that cessation of Korotkoff sounds indicate diastolic BP, while the majority of them (74%) could not identify the ideal deflation rate. In a cross-sectional study conducted among Australian nurses⁽²⁸⁾, nearly half of the participants adhered to the currently-accepted practice guidelines for measurement, sound interpretation, and cuff size assessment. Additionally, Dickson and Hajjar⁽²⁹⁾ carried out a study to enhance measurement accuracy among community-based nurses and showed

that the used technique by the majority of them was inadequate and not in accordance with the guidelines implied by the American Heart Association. Intriguingly, in a study based in Asir Central Hospital in Saudi Arabia⁽³⁰⁾, the correct patient's position during measurement was correctly declared by 22% of the participating nurses, adult cuff length by 25.2%, diastolic Korotkov sounds by 33.9%, and measuring BP to the nearest 2 mmHg in 29.1%, indicating low practice and knowledge levels.

In our study, the participating nurses adequately adhered to specific practice levels, such as elbow and back support during BP measurement and allowing the patient to rest physically prior to measurement. Nonetheless, measuring BP in both arms at least at the initial visit was correctly perceived only by 42.6% of nurses, which is in accordance with the rate of nurses' awareness (44.1%) regarding such attitude in Asir Central Hospital⁽³⁰⁾. Several recommendations have indicated the necessity of measuring BP in the contralateral arm, including the American Heart Association⁽¹⁴⁾, the Joint National Committee⁽³¹⁾, British Hypertension Society⁽³²⁾, the European Society of Hypertension and European Society of Cardiology⁽³³⁾. Heneghan et al.⁽³⁴⁾ noted that although 77% of general practitioners were aware about the relevance of BP measurement in both arms, only 30% of them have accepted this and 13% have adopted such a practice. It is possible that providing a justification for this guideline while teaching nurses is essential to ensure their adherence. Notwithstanding the lack of evidence-based explanation⁽³⁵⁾, the existence of normal inter-arm differences in systolic and diastolic BP (about 10 mmHg in 20% and 11% of patients, respectively) may lead to misdiagnosis of hypertension⁽³⁶⁾. On the other hand, Singh et al.⁽³⁷⁾ demonstrated that an inter-arm difference of > 15 mmHg is a predictor of subclavian stenosis.

In the present study, one-third of nurses were aware about the significance of asking patients about bladder emptiness. Similarly, 36.2% of nursing students correctly reported this aspect in a questionnaire-based study⁽²⁶⁾. It has been shown that bladder distention for at least 3 hours is associated with elevated systolic and diastolic BP⁽³⁸⁾, possibly due to changes in arterial plasma renin activity, sympathetic stimulation or altered psychological states^(39, 40). From another perspective, undressing patient's arm should be underscored among BP observers as indicated by the guidelines despite the controversial debate regarding its feasibility in the literature. While some studies found no significant differences in BP measurements over a sleeve or on a bare arm^(41, 42), others indicated

a significant elevation of BP values over clothed arms when compared to bare arms, particularly in the elderly^(43, 44).

However, distinct inadequate practice parameters were reported by the researcher, such as those related to measuring BP in standing position with postural hypotension suspicion, maintain correct stethoscope position. Furthermore, only 16.9% of the participating nurses perceived the importance of measuring BP twice at each visit. This was in agreement with another Spanish study, where 22% of nursing students knew that BP should be measured more than once at an outpatient clinic⁽²⁶⁾. This is especially important when using an oscillometric device for BP measurement as it may be relatively less accurate when compared to the auscultatory technique⁽⁴⁵⁾. Thus, this item should be highlighted among nurses given the high percentage of using automated devices in our study (95.4%).

In the present investigation, low practice levels were associated with lack of proper training. Recently, Zhang et al.⁽⁴⁶⁾ reported that the best BP measurements were obtained by nursing students, not the experienced ones. This might be attributable to providing regular training and practice to students as parts of their studies. Moreover, nurses in such a category are expected to follow measurement guidelines more strictly and in a practical manner. For experience nurses, they are often more engaged in nursing management rather than basic BP measurement in their daily work. As such, frequent trainings to both students and experienced nurses are required. In this context, Jones and Hall⁽⁴⁷⁾ supported the fundamental role of frequent training and practice along with recertification, which led to reducing observer-related BP measurement variability.

In this study, we used two tools for data collection, which included self-reported assessment by using a specific questionnaire and an examiner-filled checklist with several measurement standards. The utilized observer-assessed questionnaire showed high reliability, which could add to the strengths of our outcomes. On the other hand, nurses were observed during a unique performance of BP measurement, which may not be representative of the routine and diastolic BP⁽³⁸⁾, possibly due to changes in arterial plasma renin activity, sympathetic stimulation or altered psychological states^(39, 40). From another perspective, undressing patient's arm should be underscored among BP observers as indicated by the guidelines despite the controversial debate regarding its feasibility in the literature. While some studies

found no significant differences in BP measurements over a sleeve or on a bare arm^(41, 42), others indicated a significant elevation of BP values over clothed arms when compared to bare arms, particularly in the elderly^(43, 44).

However, distinct inadequate practice parameters were reported by the researcher, such as those related to measuring BP in standing position with postural hypotension suspicion, maintain correct stethoscope position. Furthermore, only 16.9% of the participating nurses perceived the importance of measuring BP twice at each visit. This was in agreement with another Spanish study, where 22% of nursing students knew that BP should be measured more than once at an outpatient clinic⁽²⁶⁾. This is especially important when using an oscillometric device for BP measurement as it may be relatively less accurate when compared to the auscultatory technique⁽⁴⁵⁾. Thus, this item should be highlighted among nurses given the high percentage of using automated devices in our study (95.4%).

In the present investigation, low practice levels were associated with lack of proper training. Recently, Zhang et al.⁽⁴⁶⁾ reported that the best BP measurements were obtained by nursing students, not the experienced ones. This might be attributable to providing regular training and practice to students as parts of their studies. Moreover, nurses in such a category are expected to follow measurement guidelines more strictly and in a practical manner. For experience nurses, they are often more engaged in nursing management rather than basic BP measurement in their daily work. As such, frequent trainings to both students and experienced nurses are required. In this context, Jones and Hall⁽⁴⁷⁾ supported the fundamental role of frequent training and practice along with recertification, which led to reducing observer-related BP measurement variability.

In this study, we used two tools for data collection, which included self-reported assessment by using a specific questionnaire and an examiner-filled checklist with several measurement standards. The utilized observer-assessed questionnaire showed high reliability, which could add to the strengths of our outcomes. On the other hand, nurses were observed during a unique performance of BP measurement, which may not be representative of the routine practice; especially in case of eventual factors interfering with the good practice.

CONCLUSION:

Our study showed high knowledge and practice levels for BP measurement among a sample of nurses regarding providing a pre-measurement rest to the patient, back and elbow support, cuff position, and rounding the values to 2 mmHg as well as moderate practice levels about measuring BP in both arms, undressing patients' arms and following the specific guidelines. Nonetheless, the participants exhibited inadequate practice levels regarding several parameters, including the assurance of bladder distension, measuring BP twice at each visit, and measuring BP in a standing position if postural hypotension is suspected.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

We corroborate the importance of addressing measurement errors by following the implied guidelines. This could be best approached by providing regular and frequent training to nurses, including students and more experienced nurses. While providing teaching materials, they should be supported by adequate evidence-based explanation. This would eventually raise the agreement rates and ascertain better compliance to guidelines.

REFERENCES:

1. O'Brien E, Fitzgerald D. The history of blood pressure measurement. *J Hum Hypertens.* 1994;8(2):73-84.
2. Hinman AT, Engel BT, Bickford AF. Portable blood pressure recorder. Accuracy and preliminary use in evaluating intradaily variations in pressure. *Am Heart J.* 1962;63(663-668).
3. National clinical guideline centre (UK). Hypertension: the clinical management of primary hypertension in adults: Update of Clinical Guidelines 18 and 34 [Internet]. London: Royal College of Physicians (UK); 2011.
4. Mancia G, Fagard R, Narkiewicz K, Redon J, Zanchetti A, Bohm M, et al. 2013 ESH/ESC Guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension: the Task Force for the management of arterial hypertension of the European Society of Hypertension (ESH) and of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). *J Hypertens.* 2013;31(7):1281-1357.
5. Canzanello VJ, Jensen PL, Schwartz GL. Are aneroid sphygmomanometers accurate in hospital and clinic settings? *Arch Intern Med.* 2001;161(5):729-731.
6. Shah AS, Dolan LM, D'Agostino RB, Jr., Standiford D, Davis C, Testaverde L, et al. Comparison of mercury and aneroid blood

- pressure measurements in youth. *Pediatrics*. 2012;129(5):e1205-1210.
7. Ostchega Y, Prineas RJ, Nwankwo T, Zipf G. Assessing blood pressure accuracy of an aneroid sphygmomanometer in a national survey environment. *Am J Hypertens*. 2011;24(3):322-327.
 8. Ma Y, Temprowska M, Fowler S, Prineas RJ, Montez MG, Brown-Friday J, et al. Evaluating the accuracy of an aneroid sphygmomanometer in a clinical trial setting. *Am J Hypertens*. 2009;22(3):263-266.
 9. Ogedegbe G, Pickering T. Principles and techniques of blood pressure measurement. *Cardiol Clin*. 2010;28(4):571-586.
 10. Shahbabu B, Dasgupta A, Sarkar K, Sahoo SK. Which is more accurate in measuring the blood pressure? A digital or an aneroid Sphygmomanometer. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2016;10(3):Lc11-14.
 11. Badeli H, Assadi F. Strategies to reduce pitfalls in measuring blood pressure. *Int J Prev Med*. 2014;5(Suppl 1):S17-20.
 12. Stevens SL, Wood S, Koshiaris C, Law K, Glasziou P, Stevens RJ, et al. Blood pressure variability and cardiovascular disease: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Bmj*. 2016;354(i4098).
 13. Thomas O, Shipman KE, Day K, Thomas M, Martin U, Dasgupta I. Prevalence and determinants of white coat effect in a large UK hypertension clinic population. *J Hum Hypertens*. 2016;30(6):386-391.
 14. Pickering TG, Hall JE, Appel LJ, Falkner BE, Graves J, Hill MN, et al. Recommendations for blood pressure measurement in humans and experimental animals: part 1: blood pressure measurement in humans: a statement for professionals from the Subcommittee of Professional and Public Education of the American Heart Association Council on High Blood Pressure Research. *Circulation*. 2005;111(5):697-716.
 15. Aldiab A, Shubair MM, Al-Zahrani JM, Aldossari KK, Al-Ghamdi S, Househ M, et al. Prevalence of hypertension and prehypertension and its associated cardioembolic risk factors; a population based cross-sectional study in Alkharj, Saudi Arabia. *BMC public health*. 2018;18(1):1327-1327.
 16. Becker MK, Blazovich L, Schug V, Schulenberg C, Daniels J, Neal D, et al. Nursing student caring behaviors during blood pressure measurement. *J Nurs Educ*. 2008;47(3):98-104.
 17. Rabbia F, Testa E, Rabbia S, Pratico S, Colasanto C, Montersino F, et al. Effectiveness of blood pressure educational and evaluation program for the improvement of measurement accuracy among nurses. *High Blood Press Cardiovasc Prev*. 2013;20(2):77-80.
 18. Lloyd-Jones DM, Morris PB, Ballantyne CM, Birtcher KK, Daly DD, DePalma SM, et al. 2017 Focused Update of the 2016 ACC Expert Consensus Decision Pathway on the Role of Non-Statins Therapies for LDL-Cholesterol Lowering in the Management of Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease Risk: A Report of the American College of Cardiology Task Force on Expert Consensus Decision Pathways. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2017;
 19. CDC Grand Rounds_ A Public Health Approach to Detect and Control Hypertension _ MMWR.
 20. الدم, الجمعية لرعاية السعودية. ضغط الدم; Guidelines 2018. 2018
 21. Sug S, Yoon S, Fryar CD, Carroll MD. Hypertension Prevalence and Control Among Adults: United States, 2011–2014. 2011;
 22. Screening, Treatment and Control of Hypertension in U.S. Private Physician Offices, 2003–2004.
 23. Recommendations for Blood Pressure Measurement in Humans and Experimental Animals _ *Circulation*.
 24. Rushton M, Smith J. How to measure blood pressure manually. 2016;
 25. Omboni S, Palatini P, Parati G. Standards for ambulatory blood pressure monitoring clinical reporting in daily practice: recommendations from the Italian Society of Hypertension. *Blood Press Monit*. 2015;20(5):241-244.
 26. Gonzalez-Lopez JJ, Gomez-Arnau Ramirez J, Torremocha Garcia R, Albelda Esteban S, Alio del Barrio J, Rodriguez-Artalejo F. Knowledge of correct blood pressure measurement procedures among medical and nursing students. *Rev Esp Cardiol*. 2009;62(5):568-571.
 27. Nolan J, Nolan M. Can nurses take an accurate blood pressure? *Br J Nurs*. 1993;2(14):724-729.
 28. Armstrong RS. Nurses' knowledge of error in blood pressure measurement technique. *Int J Nurs Pract*. 2002;8(3):118-126.
 29. Dickson BK, Hajjar I. Blood Pressure Measurement Education and Evaluation Program improves measurement accuracy in community-based nurses: a pilot study. *J Am Acad Nurse Pract*. 2007;19(2):93-102.
 30. Ahmed ME. Knowledge of blood pressure measurement among a teaching hospital staff in a developing nation. *J Hum Hypertens*. 1997;11(8):495-499.
 31. Chobanian AV, Bakris GL, Black HR, Cushman WC, Green LA, Izzo JL, Jr., et al. Seventh report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention,

- Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure. *Hypertension*. 2003;42(6):1206-1252.
32. Williams B, Poulter NR, Brown MJ, Davis M, McInnes GT, Potter JF, et al. Guidelines for management of hypertension: report of the fourth working party of the British Hypertension Society, 2004-BHS IV. *J Hum Hypertens*. 2004;18(3):139-185.
 33. Mancia G, De Backer G, Dominiczak A, Cifkova R, Fagard R, Germano G, et al. 2007 Guidelines for the management of arterial hypertension: The Task Force for the Management of Arterial Hypertension of the European Society of Hypertension (ESH) and of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). *Eur Heart J*. 2007;28(12):1462-1536.
 34. Heneghan C, Perera R, Mant D, Glasziou P. Hypertension guideline recommendations in general practice: awareness, agreement, adoption, and adherence. *Br J Gen Pract*. 2007;57(545):948-952.
 35. Fred HL. Accurate blood pressure measurements and the other arm: the doctor is ultimately responsible. *Tex Heart Inst J*. 2013;40(3):217-219.
 36. Lane D, Beevers M, Barnes N, Bourne J, John A, Malins S, et al. Inter-arm differences in blood pressure: when are they clinically significant? *J Hypertens*. 2002;20(6):1089-1095.
 37. Singh S, Sethi A, Singh M, Khosla K, Grewal N, Khosla S. Simultaneously measured inter-arm and inter-leg systolic blood pressure differences and cardiovascular risk stratification: a systemic review and meta-analysis. *J Am Soc Hypertens*. 2015;9(8):640-650.e612.
 38. Choi EJ, Jeong DW, Lee JG, Lee S, Kim YJ, Yi YH, et al. The impact of bladder distension on blood pressure in middle aged women. *Korean J Fam Med*. 2011;32(5):306-310.
 39. Hogenson KD. Acute postoperative hypertension in the hypertensive patient. *J Post Anesth Nurs*. 1992;7(1):38-44.
 40. Funke PJ, Prabhakar NR, Hertle L, Runkel N, Dahlheim H. Plasma renin activity and cardiovascular changes in patients with chronic bladder distension. *Urol Int*. 1982;37(5):363-368.
 41. Holleman DR, Jr., Westman EC, McCrory DC, Simel DL. The effect of sleeved arms on oscillometric blood pressure measurement. *J Gen Intern Med*. 1993;8(6):325-326.
 42. Ma G, Sabin N, Dawes M. A comparison of blood pressure measurement over a sleeved arm versus a bare arm. *CMAJ*. 2008;178(5):585-589.
 43. Ozone S, Sato M, Takayashiki A, Sato T, Matsushita A, Yoshimoto H, et al. Blood pressure measurements over thin and thick sleeves in the frail elderly. *Blood Press Monit*. 2018;23(1):9-11.
 44. Ozono S, Shaku F, Sato M, Takayashiki A, Tsutsumi M, Maeno T. Comparison of blood pressure measurements on the bare arm, over a sleeve and over a rolled-up sleeve in the elderly. *Fam Pract*. 2016;33(5):517-522.
 45. Nitzan M, Slotki I, Shavit L. More accurate systolic blood pressure measurement is required for improved hypertension management: a perspective. *Med Devices (Auckl)*. 2017;10(157-163).
 46. Zhang M, Zhang X, Chen F, Dong B, Chen A, Zheng D. Effects of room environment and nursing experience on clinical blood pressure measurement: an observational study. *Blood Press Monit*. 2017;22(2):79-85.
 47. Jones DW, Hall JE. Seventh report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure and evidence from new hypertension trials. *Hypertension*. 2004;43(1):1-3.